

ISic1665

Funerary chest of Annios Keler

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2015-01-16, Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in 1930 (acquired 01.06.1930) on the south side of Predio di Spagna (under the modern hospital), possibly in secondary deposition

Coordinates

37.073341, 15.283175

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 45780

Physical Description

A square funerary chest of the local brown limestone

Dimensions

Height 24.2 cm

Width 34 cm

Depth 30.8 cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek letters on the side of the chest

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Tall regular letters, deeply cut: Alpha with broken bar; omicron in rhomboid form; sigma lunate but square in form; kappa with short arms; epsilon standard with equal length horizontal bars; a large diamond shape interpunct in line 1

Letter heights:

Line 1: 50-60 (but omicron sigma 40-45) mm

Line 2: 62-66 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Ἄ(υ)λος · Ἄννιος

2. Κέλερ

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Aulos Annios Keler

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1950-1951. Christiana-Byzantina Siciliae II. *Nuovo Didaskaleion*. 4: 55-66. At 62 no.20

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 47 n.231

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014